

FULL PAPER – A Seamless T-shirt Design with Textile-based ECG Electrodes and Posture Monitoring Sensors

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Abstract: Wearable technologies with biosignal monitoring are growing in interest day by day owing to their high degree of flexibility, comfort, reusability, and ability for continuous and long-term monitoring. Adhesive, single-use electrodes are currently the most widespread ECG monitoring method. Nevertheless, they are not ideal for long-term monitoring since the conductive gel dries out over time, adversely affecting signal quality and frequently irritating the skin. Textile-based ECG electrodes are more user-friendly and less prone to skin irritation compared to traditional ECG electrodes since they are dry and non-adhesive. However, the drawback of textile-based electrodes is that they are more susceptible to various conditions, including contact pressure, contact surface area, and electrode location, which can affect the accuracy and dependability of ECG data recorded by e-textiles. This study aimed to improve signal quality and comfort properties while integrating the electrodes and strain sensors with seamless knitting technology. In this study, integrating ECG and posture monitoring into the seamless t-shirt offers an easy-to-use, visually unobtrusive, comfortable, and continuous method for tracking vital health metrics and detecting abnormalities over extended periods. Thanks to the textile-based capacitive strain sensors in the t-shirt, detection of the incorrect posture position that many people have today due to reasons such as having sedentary lives is possible. Capacitive sensors were selected because they have higher linearity than resistive sensors, and their repeatability outperforms the resistive sensor's performance over an extended length of time. In addition to ECG signals, ECG-derived respiratory data can also be obtained from electrodes in the future. It has been observed that the t-shirt can be an alternative to the technology used today because of its adaptability to the human body and the advantages of prolonged wearability and extended monitoring durations.

Keywords: textile-based electrodes, textile-based strain sensors, ECG monitoring, posture monitoring, seamless smart t-shirt.

1 INTRODUCTION

Relatively new technology titled electronic textiles is likely to broaden boundaries even more significantly and has already opened the potential for garments in the sports, medical, defense, and health monitoring fields. [1] The primary advantage of wearable health monitoring systems is continuous real-time monitoring, made possible by continuously tracking sensors embedded in clothing or accessories. [2] Gathering biopotential signals for daily and personal health monitoring is a significant use of e-textiles in the sensor area. It is anticipated that biopotential signals provided by wearable systems as biofeedback will transform several kinds of technologies, such as rehabilitation tools and point-of-care health monitoring devices. [3].

The ECG signals have been widely utilized to monitor human cardiac activity and assess cardiac and circulatory functioning [4] and can represent the electrical activity of the heart muscles [5]. Adhesive, single-use electrodes are currently the traditional ECG monitoring method. These wet electrodes consist of an adhesive cushion to enhance contact with the skin and a gel layer to lower the skin-electrode contact impedance. [6] Nevertheless, these electrodes are not ideal for long-term use since the

conductive gel dries up with time, reducing signal quality and frequently creating discomfort and skin irritation to the user [7]. Textile-based gel-free, "dry" electrodes can be good options for wearable, long-term point-of-care personal health monitoring applications, in addition to many other similar systems, even though wet electrodes are the norm in clinical settings. While permeability to air and moisture reduces the risk of skin irritations, flexibility is crucial primarily for enabling skin-compatible devices by conforming to the human body's natural shape, providing wearability, and achieving better skin–electrode coupling. [3]

Recent research indicates that wearable conductive textiles offer a practical replacement to conventional ECG monitoring electrodes. In 2005, Wainwright and David Bychkov designed the first-ever ECG Bio-Physical display jacket. In 2015, Ralph Lauren and OM Signal introduced the "Polotech shirt". "The Polotech" shirt was made of smart t-shirt with textile-based electrodes, including Bluetooth, a motion detector, a heart rate and pulse rate monitor, and more. [8] In 2016, Boehm et al. designed a 12-lead ECG t-shirt with ten fully active and dry electrodes as well as an ECG recorder. They integrated comfortable

patches of conductive textile into the ECG T-shirt to replace the adhesive gel electrodes. The textile patches serve as electrodes, and they are connected to the outside of the T-shirt by snap fasteners. To prevent signal deterioration, they attached active circuits on the outside of the T-shirt to further improve the signal quality of the dry electrodes. [9]

There is a growing need for soft sensors that can monitor body movements continuously. These sensors are used in various applications, such as human-machine interfaces and measuring physiological parameters. Soft sensors are preferred because they provide accurate measurements while being comfortable for the user and can be easily integrated into wearable garments. [10] Stretchable, soft strain sensors are becoming increasingly popular due to their wide range of applications. [11] Textile-based strain sensors offer significant benefits for posture monitoring due to their ability to seamlessly integrate into clothing, offering a practical and wearable alternative to traditional motion capture systems for monitoring physiological signals. [12,13] One key advantage of textile-based strain sensors is their flexibility and durability, making them suitable for continuous monitoring during various daily activities, including running and other physical exercises. The sensor can also detect small changes in human activity and the contraction of the muscles. [14] Soft sensors have the ability to obtain precise measurements in proximity to the human body, and they can be easily incorporated into wearable clothing. [10] Compared to resistive sensors, capacitive sensors exhibit better hysteresis and reaction times, which is advantageous for wearable applications where sensors are subjected to repetitive dynamic pressures. [15,16] Building capacitive-based soft sensors can be accomplished by sandwiching a dielectric layer between two conformable electrodes. When the two primary parameters—electrode area and dielectric thickness—alter geometrically in response to applied strain, a capacitance change takes place. [10]

The increase in sedentary lifestyles has become a significant public health concern globally. Sedentary behaviors, characterized by prolonged sitting or low levels of physical activity, have been associated with various health risks and conditions. [17] People who lead sedentary lifestyles have been shown to have a higher risk of developing musculoskeletal issues, and sedentary jobs are frequently associated with neck and shoulder symptoms. [18]

In 2020, Jin et al. designed a garment to be worn as an undershirt and was made as a single piece. Eight sensors were sewed around the shoulder joint of the shirt to monitor shoulder joint kinematics in 3 degree-of-freedom, including rotations around the arm's longitudinal axis, for both cyclic and random arm movements. [19]

In this study, we have introduced a novel seamless t-shirt design capable of performing 3-lead ECG measurements and posture monitoring thanks to the seamless integration of textile-based electrodes and capacitive strain sensors.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

While integrating the ECG electrodes and strain sensors into this seamless smart t-shirt design, the main yarn consisted of 93% polyamide and 7% elastane. Elastane core yarn was additionally fed into the machine, whereas the conductive yarn was SHIELDEX 78/18 DTEX, Z turns + B silver plated yarn. Ecoflex 00-30 (SmoothOn, USA) was utilized as a dielectric layer.

The Ad8232 was used to amplify the ECG signal, and an Arduino microcontroller was used to capture it at a 100 Hz sample rate. After that, the recorded signal was digitally filtered using a notch filter at 50 Hz and a high-pass filter at 0.5 Hz using Python Neurokit. Regarding the data of strain sensors, the values received from the sensors were collected and recorded using the "ArduSpreadSheet" (Arduino software) at a sampling rate of 50Hz.

2.2 Methods

A textile-based electrode system comprising three textile-based electrodes and three capacitive strain sensors for posture monitoring has been manufactured seamlessly using a Santoni circular 15-inch diameter knitting machine. After the product was machine knitted, it was washed in a domestic laundry machine at 90 °C.

Figure 1 a) Positions of the textile-based 3-lead ECG electrodes, b) positions of the posture-monitoring strain sensors. c) location of the rib pattern on the t-shirt

The t-shirt was produced with two layers, and the electrodes were located in the inner layer, which was in contact with the body. A sponge has been added between the inner and outer layers to increase the pressure of the electrodes on the body as it was essential for better signal quality that the product fitted the participant's body well and creates pressure towards the body. For this reason, the area containing the product's ECG electrodes was designed in a 1*1 rib knit pattern, while the rest of the t-shirt was knitted in a jersey pattern. The electrode areas had a jersey knit pattern to provide a broader surface area of contact with the skin, whereas the strain sensors had a pique knit design as issues have arisen in the jersey pattern trials for strain sensors due to the use of different yarn qualities.

Since short circuit problems were encountered when uncoated fabric was used to create a dielectric layer, Ecoflex 00-30 silicon coating was applied on a glass surface and was dried at room conditions for 24 hours. Then, they were applied on the top of one conductive side of the capacitive strain sensors, Ecoflex 00-30 silicon was used as an adhesive to attach them. To hinder the short circuit problem, the silicon piece was snipped 1 cm bigger

than the sensors' sizes. Lastly, the collar and sleeves were sewn to the body piece.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 ECG Monitoring

Figure 2 shows the raw and filtered ECG signals which were recorded while the participant was sitting. Especially, the R peaks, which are necessary to observe heart rate (HR), in other words the number of beats per minute (bpm), and the R-R interval (the interval between heartbeats), were clearly visible.

Figure 2 Raw and filtered ECG data recorded with the smart t-shirt.

3.2 Posture Monitoring

Figure 3 illustrates the difference between the capacitance value that sensors had while the wearer was sitting with a correct posture position and wrong posture positions. While the former caused having a decrease in the capacitance value, the latter resulted to reach higher values. This suggests that the dynamic changes correlated with varying degrees of physical activity are well captured and observed by textile-based strain sensors.

Figure 3 Raw and filtered capacitance values during correct and wrong posture of shoulders

4 CONCLUSION

Wearable technologies with biosignal monitoring are becoming popular for their flexibility, comfort, and long-term monitoring. Textile-based devices have the ability to measure human body movements and physiological data, such as heart rate. Additionally, textile-based strain sensors provide a versatile and effective solution for posture monitoring, offering benefits such as comfort, flexibility, durability, and high sensitivity. These sensors have the potential to revolutionize the field of wearable monitoring systems by enabling accurate and real-time tracking of human motions and postures.

In this study, we designed a smart garment capable of monitoring the wearer's heart rate and posture. This study highlights that the transition to a textile structure not only adds functionality but also generates unique behavior, benefitting physical therapy, telemedicine, virtual reality, and sports performance tracking. This garment design can improve comfort by integrating electrodes and strain sensors with seamless knitting technology into a t-shirt for easy and continuous tracking of vital health metrics. In the future, this t-shirt can offer prolonged wearability and extended monitoring durations and be an alternative to current wearables.

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